

Literature Review of Research on Influential Factors on Community Music Participation of Elderly Groups in Chengdu City

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Abstract: *As aging increases in Chengdu, community music, as an important vehicle for promoting mental health and alleviating social isolation among the elderly, has become a key issue in the construction of an “all-age-friendly” city. In this paper, we review the literature on community music participation in Chengdu and explore the implications of the factors affecting community music participation among older adults, categorized by community development and function, problems and suggestions, and factors affecting community music participation.*

Keywords: Community music participation; Older adults; Literature review.

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1. Introduction

China is accelerating into a deeply aging society. Data from the seventh national census show that China's population aged 60 and above has reached 264 million in 2020, accounting for 18.7% of the total population, and is expected to exceed 400 million by 2035. Chengdu City, as a populous city in western China, has a total population of 20 million, of which the proportion of elderly people aged 60 and above reaches 21.34% (Chengdu Bureau of Statistics, 2021), which has entered the stage of super-aging society in advance. Some related studies have shown that the participation rate of community activities among the elderly declined by 62% after retirement (Zhao, 2020), and 89% of the elderly expressed a desire for cultural activity participation, but 78% believed that the existing community activities were single (Li & Zhang, 2020).

As a city with deep cultural heritage and musical traditions, Chengdu has been vigorously promoting the construction of an international music capital in recent years, and has been actively carrying out a variety of community music promotion activities. The Chengdu Bureau of Culture, Radio, Television and Tourism pointed out in the “Implementation Opinions of the Chengdu Municipal People's Government on Supporting the Development of the Music Industry and Promoting the Construction of the International Music Capital” that: “During the 14th Five-Year Plan period, we will continue to intensify the publicity of the construction of Chengdu's international music capital and the development of the music industry, carry out promotional activities to enhance the attractiveness of the city's music culture and influence of the city's music culture, and to stimulate the public's enthusiasm for participating in music life (Chengdu Culture, Radio, Television and Tourism Bureau, 2022).

2. Literature Search Methods and Characterization

This paper tries to analyze the existing research field of community music by searching “community music” as the keyword in China Knowledge Network as the data source, and comprehensively utilizing both qualitative and quantitative methods, in order to understand a more comprehensive viewpoint of the related field.

Among the retrieved literature, there are a total of 854 pieces of related literature in all types. The earliest Chinese scholars who studied community music started from 1991, and there have been more than 30 years so far, but there are very few researchers in the two decades from 1991-2010, and the number of researchers gradually rises from 2020, and the number of researchers reaches the peak from 2021 and 2023, as can be seen in Figure 1, can be seen. The status of research in 2025 is not yet clear as the year 2025 is not yet over.

Figure 1: Annual distribution map of community music literature Source:CNKI(2024)

The literature publication period was set to 2020-2025, and 66 articles were retrieved, with the largest amount of literature on the themes of community music culture and community music education, followed by community music activities.

3. Key Elements and Perspectives of the Literature

3.1 The Development and Function of Community Music

The International Society for Music Education (ISME) Committee on Community Music Activities, founded in 1982, is today the most influential academic organization for international community music research: since 1988, the Committee on Community Music Education, which meets every two years in advance of the World Conference on Music Education, has greatly advanced the development of community music by organizing the Committee’s Colloquium. The themes of the Commission’s previous symposia are as follows (Figure 1): (Xiahou, 2023).

Table 1: Themes of previous seminars of the Commission Source:Xiahou(2023)

Times	Sites	Theme of the seminar
1988	Wellington, New Zealand	Community music-interaction between amateurs and professionals
1990	Oslo, Norway	Training of musicians and music educators to meet community needs
1992	Auckland, New Zealand	The Role of Music Educators in a Multicultural Society
1994	Athens, Georgia, USA	The Role of Community Music in a Changing World
1996	Liverpool, England	Meeting the challenges of the twenty-first century
1998	Durban, South Africa	Multiple genres of music - Loop Loop
2000	Toronto, Canada	Vibrant music, shared music-making: community music in the new millennium
2002	Rotterdam, Netherlands	Five themes of community music
2004	Tenerife, Spain	Community music at a critical time
2006	Singaporean	Building partnerships, making connections, catalysing change
2008	Rome, Italy	Projects, perspectives and dialogue
2010	Hangzhou, China	Community Music Creates Harmony
2012	Corfu, Greece	Global initiatives from history to the twenty-first century
2014	Salvador, Brazil	Listening to the World: Experiencing and Connecting with Knowledge from the Music of the Community
2014	Edinburgh, Scotland	Innovation and change in community music
2018	Tbilisi, Georgia	Sparking Curiosity: Celebrating the Diverse Voices of Community Music

Ma (2022) shows in his research that community music has an educational function, and that community music education is an important carrier for the construction of advanced socialist culture with Chinese characteristics, which helps to realize the fundamental task of establishing morality, helps to build a harmonious society shared by all people, and helps to carry forward the excellent culture of the Chinese nation. In response to these problems, the countermeasures of mining value implication, expanding social participation, strengthening moral education penetration, innovating inheritance path, and insisting on cultural self-confidence can provide reference for the realization of the fundamental task of establishing morality and educating people in community music education in the new era.

Qin (2023) showed in his research that community music has a leisure and entertainment function, and the most important function of community music construction is leisure and entertainment. It is because the theme is more relaxed and the form of activities is diversified that community residents tend to voluntarily participate in the activities of urban community music culture and realize the purpose of relaxation in the activities. Therefore, urban community music and cultural activities can attract the participation of community residents and help them to regulate their emotions, relax their bodies and minds, and entertain themselves.

3.2 Issues and Recommendations for Community Music

Guo (2022) China's urban community music culture has a late start, a weak foundation, a lack of theoretical aspects, participants tend to age, and the ratio of men to women is unreasonable, etc. Wang (2021) China's community music culture construction is not enough motivation; the overall development of community music culture is not balanced; the development of community music culture reflects an unevenness; the degree of innovation of community music culture is not enough; the degree of innovation of community music culture; community Music and cultural services are not targeted; macro-level policy aspects of the support is not enough, the item cause to long-term healthy development, there must be corresponding policy norms to escort. Ding(2020) research shows that: the age and gender range of participants in community music activities is narrower, the participants are obviously middle-aged and old-aged retired people, and shows a trend of comprehensive aging, the survey found that more than 70% of the residents involved in community music activities are retired middle-aged and old-aged people over 55 years old, of which the proportion of women is greater. Lin (2022) government lack of policy and financial support for the development of community music and culture, local government participation in the construction of urban community music and culture, to a certain extent, determines the quality of the development of music and cultural content, practical activities.

Li's study(2022) puts forward suggestions for the development of community music: to gain a deeper understanding of the needs of community residents and to respect the needs and feelings of the people; to satisfy the needs of the cultural life of people of different age levels in the community, so that music and cultural activities can cover all the people, the elderly, the young and middle-aged, and the children; and to enrich the way of organizing and practicing community music activities. Qin (2023) pointed out that the development of community music needs to strengthen the support and participation of the government and the community in the construction of urban community music; it is necessary to strengthen publicity to attract community residents to participate in urban community music and cultural activities, and to build a professional urban community music construction team. Ma (2022) pointed out in his study that community music needs to explore the value and meaning, expand social participation, strengthen moral education, innovate inheritance paths, and insist on cultural confidence, and other countermeasures that can provide reference for the realization of the fundamental task of moral education in community music in the new era.

3.3 Influences on Community Music Participation

3.3.1 Impact of individual needs on community music participation

In her study, Tong (2023) found that participation in community activities was mainly influenced by factors such as individual age and physical and mental health factors, hobbies and interpersonal interactions, family structure and household income, venues and farm time, dance difficulty and dance team atmosphere, professional guidance and social support. Among these major influences, the most important influences were physical and mental health, interpersonal interactions, dance team atmosphere, and age, followed by hobbies, venues and farm leisure time, and then family income and other influences.

Huang's (2020) findings showed that the factors affecting participation in community activities are mainly

personal factors, and leisure time and current mood are the primary considerations; whether or not there are companions, leisure time, how the current mood is, and whether or not the music is appealing are important influences on the exercise adherence behaviors of the people who participate in square dance exercise.

Zhang (2020) through the analysis of the current situation of the development of community music in Xuzhou, China, concluded that there is a deviation between the supply of music in the community out of the district and the demand of the residents, at present, Xuzhou City involves the community music to carry out the form of square dance, opera type organizations, choirs, senior university, etc., the main coverage of the crowd is the middle-aged and elderly groups, the content of education is mainly based on the study of vocal music, dance learning, instrumental learning, the second, music The basic theory of music and culture and music appreciation are fewer, and the contents are relatively single, and there is no education content that can cover all age and gender groups, which makes the music education needs of some groups of people not satisfied.

Lin (2021) found that community music could not meet the individual differences and diversified needs of residents, and that each resident as an individual is bound to have individual differences and diverse needs. The individual differences of residents are the most basic criteria for community activities. However, according to the results of the survey, most of the community staff hold the attitude that providing services to residents is the completion of the work, and seldom understand the needs of the residents in depth. Although it is impossible to realize the needs of the residents in their entirety, they should reasonably take into account the needs of the majority of the residents, and then refine and adjust the requirements of the residents who have special needs, and satisfy them in a selective manner.

3.3.2 Research on the impact of community environment on community music participation

Xie & Guo (2020) found that community infrastructure and teacher strength directly affect the quality of community music education and residents' participation, for example, the completeness of teaching facilities, such as the configuration of music classrooms and the completeness of electric pianos and multimedia equipment, can effectively promote the development of community music education and increase the residents' motivation to participate.

In their study, Chen & Chen (2022) found that the lack of teachers is still a challenge, and many community music teachers are mainly part-time music teachers from neighboring schools, and the lack of full-time teachers restricts the in-depth development of community music education, and the improvement of the community environment, including the enhancement of teaching facilities and teachers, is crucial for promoting residents' active participation in community music activities. Studies have shown that the degree of improvement of the community environment directly affects the motivation and depth of residents' participation in community music, and that complete teaching facilities and adequate teacher strength are key factors in promoting the quality of community music.

Lin's (2021) study shows that many current community environments still have many problems that constrain the development of community music activities and resident participation, and that the level of construction of community environments is closely related to residents' motivation to participate in community music activities. The infrastructure of the community environment and the degree of cooperation among the staff play a key role in the successful implementation of music activities, while at the same time, the professional competence and service attitude of the community music teachers have also become key factors.

Xie, (2023) study shows that. The imbalance between residents' growing demand and social supply is prominent; community public places, access to information on community residents' activities, lack of community guidance and other issues related to the community environment can directly affect residents' participation in community activities.

3.3.3 Research on the impact of social resources on community music participation

Social resources play an important role in promoting community music participation, and Xie & Guo's (2020) study points out that the adoption of the "government + market" model, in which the government and market capital jointly participate in the construction of community services, can effectively enhance the level of comprehensive community services. Through the introduction of high-quality services, to meet the multi-level needs of residents, improve the community supporting facilities, and enhance the quality of life of residents. This

model not only reduces the government's financial pressure, but also provides residents with high-quality services and products.

Lin (2021) showed that: the current music and cultural activities in many communities are mainly government-oriented content, the lack of a perfect community music and cultural system, which leads to a single content of the activities, and it is difficult to comprehensively improve the music and cultural literacy of the residents. Therefore, it is particularly important to improve the community music and culture system, enrich the content of activities and meet the diverse needs of residents. Fei (2023) showed in his study that social resources and policy factors of local policies, national policies can become a direct positive impact on youth sports participation.

4. Review of Research

Existing research has three limitations: there is a clear disciplinary divide in the exploration of factors influencing community music participation: music pedagogy focuses on individual needs (Huang & Guo, 2023), sociology focuses on the community environment (Xie & Guo, 2020), and public administration scholars pay attention to policy resources (Lin, 2021). Secondly, individual motivation and environmental support are viewed separately, without the support of social-ecological system theory and the framework of integration analysis; thirdly, regional cultural characteristics are neglected, and it is unclear how the tension between the tradition of "slow life" and the impact of modernization in Chengdu can regulate the effectiveness of music participation.

In this study, an integrated model will be constructed: using the social-ecological system theory as a framework, incorporating individual needs, community environment, and social support into a unified analytical system, and exploring cross-level interaction effects.

We will analyze how regional music culture, through habitual shaping, affects older adults' participation preferences.

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